

AMENABILITY OF $ap(S)$

A.M. Aminpour¹, Mehrdad Seilani²

¹*Department of Mathematical Sciences and computer, Shahid Chamran University, Ahvaz, Iran*

²*Iranian Academic Center for Education, Culture and Research*

Corresponding email address: A.M.Aminpour@scu.ac.ir; Seilanimaths@yahoo.com

Abstract

In this paper, we present an important new theorem for amenability of $ap(S)$. The set of all almost periodic functions on S is denoted by $ap(S)$. We develop the fundamental theory of almost periodic function on a general semitopological semigroup. Principal result are that $ap(S)$ is amenable if and only if $ap(S) = Sap(S) \oplus F0$ [theorem 3.1].

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I. Introduction

In the present paper we shall produce and study amenability of almost periodic semigroup S . We recall that $K(S)$ is the intersection of all the ideal of a semigroup S and $B(S)$ is the C^* -algebra of all bounded complex-valued functions on S . Note that if F is a translation invariant linear subspace of $B(S)$, then R_s and L_s are bounded linear operators on F . For $\mu \in F^*$, the left introversion operator determined by μ is the mapping $T_\mu : F \rightarrow B(S)$ defined by

$$(T_\mu f)(s) = \mu(L_s f) \quad (f \in F, s \in S)$$

The right introversion operator determined by μ is the mapping $U_\mu :$

$$F \rightarrow B(S) \text{ defined by } (U_\mu f)(s) = \mu(R_s f).$$

An m -admissible subalgebra of $B(S)$ is a translation invariant, left m -introverted C^* -subalgebra of $B(S)$ containing the constant functions [1].

The main purpose of this paper is to show that if S be a semitopological semigroup then $ap(S)$ is amenable if and only if $ap(S) = Sap(S) \oplus F0$ where $Sap(S)$ is space of strongly almost periodic functions on S . Let $F0 = \{f \in ap(S), 0 \in (R_s f^-)\}$, where the closure of $R_s f$ is taken in the topology P of pointwise convergence on S [theorem 3.3].

JOHNF. Berglund [1] introduced the concept of weakly almost periodic functions in order to show amenability of $Wap(S)$. Hewitt [2] pointed out that the theories of amenability of $Sap(S)$ are the same. We conclude by establishing some properties of $ap(S)$, for example $ap(S)$ is left amenable

if and only if $\text{ap}(S) = \text{Sap}(S) \oplus H$ for some left translation invariant, closed, linear subspace H of $\text{ap}(S)$.

II. Definitions and preliminaries

Definition 2.1. Let S be a semitopological semigroup. A function $f \in C(S)$ is said to be almost periodic if the set $R_s f$ of right translates of f is norm relatively compact in $C(S)$.

$\text{ap}(S)$ is a translation invariant introverted C^* -subalgebra of $C(S)$ containing the constant functions [1]. In particular $\text{ap}(S)$ is m -admissible and

$$R_s R_t f \subset R_s f, \quad R_s L_t f = L_t R_s f$$

$$R_s (f + g) \subset R_s f + R_s g, \quad R_s (fg) \subset (R_s f)(R_s g)$$

$$R_s (cf) = c R_s f, \quad \overline{R_s f} = R_s \bar{f}$$

Definition 2.2. A function $f \in C(S)$ is said weakly almost periodic if $R_s f$ is weakly (i.e. $\sigma(C(S), C(S)^*)$) relatively compact in $C(S)$.

The set of all weakly almost periodic functions on S is denoted by $W\text{ap}(S)$. It is clear that $\text{ap}(S) \subset W\text{ap}(S)$, and there are some instances where equality holds. For example, if S is a compact topological semigroup or a totally bounded topological group on the other hand, if S is a locally compact, non-compact, topological group, then the two spaces are far from being equal:

in fact, $C_0(S) \setminus \{0\} \subset W\text{ap}(S) \setminus \text{ap}(S)$. Now, we define a type of almost periodicity, called strong almost periodicity, for which the corresponding F -compactification of a semitopological semigroups is a universal topological group compactification of S [3].

Definition 2.3. A finite dimensional unitary representation of a semitopological semigroup S is a homomorphism U from S into the group of unitary operators on some finite dimensional complex Hilbert space H . The mapping $S \rightarrow \langle U_s x, y \rangle: S \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ ($x, y \in H$) are called coefficients of the representation U . If each coefficient is continuous, then U is said to be continuous [2].

The space $\text{Sap}(S)$ of strongly almost periodic functions on S is defined as the closed linear span in $C(S)$ of the set of all coefficients of continuous, finite dimensional, unitary representations of S . Equivalently, $\text{Sap}(S)$ is the closed linear span in $C(S)$ of the Matrix entries arising from the continuous, finite dimensional, unitary representation of S by [1], the $\text{Sap}(S)$ is a translation invariant, introverted C^* -subalgebra of $\text{ap}(S)$ containing the constant function.

In particular $\text{Sap}(S)$ is m -admissible, and it is easy to see that $\text{Sap}(S) \subset \text{ap}(S) \subset W\text{ap}(S)$.

III. Amenability of $ap(S)$

Before we state the next theorem we introduce some convenient notation. Let F be an m -admissible subalgebra of $C(S)$ and let $\mu \in LIM(F)$. Define $F_0 = \{f \in F : 0 \in (R_s f^-)\}$, where the closure of $R_s f$ is taken in the topology P of pointwise convergence on S , and define

$$F_\mu := \{f \in F : \mu(|f|) = 0\}, \quad \mu \in LIM(F)$$

It is readily verified that both F_0 and F_μ are left translation invariant, norm closed, conjugate closed subsets of F . Moreover, F_μ is a proper ideal of F , and F_0 has all the properties of a proper ideal of F except possibly closure under addition.

The following theorem is stated only for the left amenable case. We leave the formulation and proof the right amenable version to the reader.

Theorem 3.1. Let S be a semitopological semigroup. Then the following statements are equivalent:

- i) $ap(S)$ is left amenable;
- ii) $ap(S) = Sap(S) \oplus H$ for some left translation invariant, closed, linear subspace H of $ap(S)$;
- iii) there exists a projection of $ap(S)$ onto $Sap(S)$ that commutes with left translation;
- iv) if (ψ, X) is an $ap(S)$ -compactification of S , then for any minimal idempotent e in X the compactification $(\rho_e \circ \psi, X_e)$ is an Sap -compactification of S , where $\rho_e : X \rightarrow X_e$ denotes right translation by e . Furthermore, if (i) holds, then for any extreme LIM μ on F

$$F = Sap(S) \oplus F_\mu \quad \text{and} \quad F_\mu \subset F_0$$

Proof. (i) implies (iv). If $ap(S)$ is left amenable and if e is a minimal idempotent in X , then $X_e = eX_e$ is a compact topological group and $\rho_e \circ \psi : S \rightarrow X_e$ is a continuous homomorphism onto a dense subsemigroup of X_e . Therefore $(\rho_e \circ \psi, X_e)$ is a topological group compactification of S . If (ϕ, Y) is another such compactification of S , then $\phi^*(C(Y)) \subset Sap(S) \subset ap(S)$, hence there exists a continuous homomorphism $\pi : (\psi, X) \rightarrow (\phi, Y)$, $\pi(\rho_e(\psi(s))) = \pi(\psi(s))\pi(e) = \pi(\psi(s)) = \phi(s)$, ($s \in S$). It follows that $(\rho_e \circ \psi, X_e) \geq (\phi, Y)$. Therefore $(\rho_e \circ \psi, X_e)$ is a universal topological group compactification of S .

(iv) implies (iii). For any minimal idempotent e in X ; the left intro- version operator $T_e : ap(S) \rightarrow ap(S)$ is a projection since $T_e^2 = T_e$. Furthermore T_e commutes with each L_s . Now, by Tietz, extension theorem, $\rho_e^*(C(X_e)) = ReC$

(X). Hence if (iv) holds then $\text{Sap}(S) = (\text{pe} \circ \psi)^*(C(X, e)) = \psi^*(\text{Re}(C(X)))$. Since $\psi^*\text{Re} = \text{Te}\psi$, we obtain $\text{Sap}(S) = \text{Teap}(S)$, which shows that Te is the required projection.

(iii) implies (ii). If $P : \text{ap}(S) \rightarrow \text{Sap}(S)$ is a projection onto $\text{Sap}(S)$ such that $P L_s = L_s P$ for all $s \in S$, then $H = P^{-1}(0)$ is a closed left translation invariant subspace of $\text{ap}(S)$ such that $\text{ap}(S) = \text{Sap}(S) \oplus H$.

(ii) implies (i). Let P denote the projection of $\text{ap}(S)$ onto $\text{Sap}(S)$ defined by the direct sum, and let V be the unique invariant mean on $\text{Sap}(S)$. For any $s \in S$ and $f \in \text{ap}(S)$, $L_s P f \in \text{Sap}(S)$ and $L_s(f - P f) \in H$, Hence $P L_s f - L_s P f = P L_s(f - P f) = 0$ therefore P commutes with left translation, hence $V \circ P$ is a LIM on $\text{ap}(S)$. Now assume that (i) through (iv) hold, and let μ be extreme LIM on $\text{ap}(S)$. There is a minimal idempotent $e \in X$ such that $\mu(f) = \int G f(x) dx$, ($f \in \text{ap}(S)$) where G is the compact topological group $X_e = eX_e$, dx is normalized Haar measure on G , and

$\psi^*(f) = f$ for all $f \in \text{ap}(S)$. Then $\mu(|f|) = 0$ if and only if $\text{Re } f^* = 0$, and since $\psi^*(\text{Re } f^*) = \text{Te } f$. We see that $F\mu = \text{Te}^{-1}(0)$.

By the proof that (iv) implies (iii), $\text{ap}(S) = \text{Sap}(S) \oplus F\mu$, and since $(R_s f -) = T_x f$, $F\mu \subset F_0$.

Definition 3.2. Let S be a semitopological semigroup and let F be an m -admissible subalgebra of $C(S)$. Any compactification (ψ, X) of S such that $\psi^*(C(X)) = F$ is called an F -compactification and (ε, SF) is called the canonical F -compactification of S .

The following result is the amenable version of theorem 3.1.

Theorem 3.3. Let S be a semitopological semigroup then $\text{ap}(S)$ is amenable if and only if F_0 is an ideal in $\text{ap}(S)$ and $\text{ap}(S) = \text{Sap}(S) \oplus F_0$. In this case $F_0 = F\mu$, where μ is the unique invariant mean on $\text{ap}(S)$.

Proof. By theorem 3.1, it suffices to prove that if $\text{ap}(S)$ is amenable then $F_0 \subset F\mu$, where μ is the unique invariant mean on $\text{ap}(S)$ [4]. Now, if $f \in F_0$, then the set $I = \{x \in \text{Sap}(S) : T_x f = 0\}$ is nonempty and is a closed left ideal of $\text{Sap}(S)$. Hence I contains a minimal idempotent e . Since $K(\text{Sap}(S))$ is a group, it follows from the last part of the proof theorem 3.1 that $\text{Te}^{-1}(0) = F\mu$. Therefore, $f \in F\mu$, as required.

Example 3.4. Let $S = (\mathbb{R}_+, +)$. We shall use theorem 3.3 to show that $\text{ap}(S) = \text{Sap}(\mathbb{R}_+, +) \oplus C_0(S)$. According to theorem 3.3, for any $f \in \text{ap}(S)$ we may write $f = g + h$, where $g \in \text{Sap}(S)$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} R_{t_n} h = 0$ for some sequence $\{t_n\}$ in

S. Clearly, $h \in C^0(S)$ and g may be extended to a function $g_1 \in \text{ap}(R, +)$, $g_1|_{R^+} = g$.

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